

ASSESSING FEASIBILITY OF INTRODUCING A MARKET TO BARANGAY TANAGAN, CALATAGAN, BATANGAS: A COMPREHENSIVE STUDY

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Abstract

This study delves into the feasibility of introducing a market in Barangay Tanagan, Calatagan, Batangas, with a primary focus on assessing its viability and potential impact on local economic development. Utilizing survey questionnaires and employing statistical analysis techniques, the research gathered data from a carefully selected sample of 366 residents out of the total population of 4,224. The study evaluates both the potential benefits and challenges associated with establishing the proposed market. Findings, subjected to thorough analysis through methods such as frequency counts and weighted mean calculations, provide valuable insights into discernible patterns, emerging trends, and relevant correlations. This analytical approach contributes to a pragmatic perspective that informs and guides future studies in the field. The study reveals an interest among respondents in the establishment of public markets in their vicinity, recognizing its potential to bolster the barangay and attract diverse opportunities. The anticipated positive impact extends to fostering economic growth and enhancing local commerce in Barangay Tanagan. Consequently, based on these compelling findings, the researchers advocate for a proposal outlining the establishment of a public market in Barangay Tanagan as a means of addressing the identified needs and aspirations of the community.

Keywords: *Feasibility Study, Public Market, Barangay Tanagan*

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Introduction

The evolution of the marketplace for essential goods was a fascinating journey, molded by a myriad of historical factors. In the early stages, customer preferences were intricately tied to local availability and cultural traditions, reflecting the self-sustaining nature of early communities. This paradigm shifted as trade routes expanded, civilizations developed, and customers began seeking products from distant lands, ushering in new tastes and preferences.

A poignant example of this historical evolution was found in Calatagan, Batangas, a coastal municipality nestled in the heart of the Philippines. This picturesque region, home to approximately 56,000 residents as of the 2020 Philippine Statistics Authority (PSA) census, was not only celebrated for its natural beauty but also boasted a rich cultural heritage. The economic lifeblood of Calatagan flowed through agriculture, fishing, and tourism, as highlighted by Mercado et al. (2018). Understanding the economic dynamics of such locales was imperative, especially when considering the centrality of the market for basic necessities within the broader economy.

However, despite the rich history and economic significance of markets for basic necessities, a noticeable research gap exists concerning the nuanced dynamics and challenges faced by such markets in specific localities, particularly in coastal municipalities like Calatagan and Batangas. While existing literature explored the broader economic impact of basic necessity markets, there was limited insight into the unique socio-economic factors, consumer behaviors, and challenges that influenced the success or hindrance of these markets in coastal regions. This research aimed to address this gap by providing a localized and in-depth analysis of the market for basic necessities in Calatagan, contributing valuable insights to the broader field of economic studies.

The objectives of the study aligned closely with this mission. First, the study sought to analyze and understand the economic dynamics of Calatagan, Batangas, focusing on the interplay between agriculture, fishing, tourism, and the market for basic necessities. Second, it aimed to investigate the preferences, purchasing behaviors, and evolving needs of consumers in Calatagan regarding essential goods, including food, clothing, and household items. Third, the research aimed to identify the unique challenges and opportunities faced by businesses operating in the market for basic necessities in a coastal municipality context, with the ultimate goal of offering practical recommendations for improvement. Additionally, the study aimed to evaluate the direct and indirect impact of a thriving market for basic necessities on employment rates, business revenues, and overall economic stability in Calatagan. Finally, based on these findings, the study endeavored to propose practical recommendations for local businesses to adapt and thrive in the ever-evolving landscape of consumer preferences and economic conditions.

By addressing these objectives, the study sought to fill the identified research gap and contribute valuable insights that could inform local policies, guide business strategies, and enhance our understanding of the intricate relationship between basic necessity markets and the socio-economic fabric of coastal communities like Calatagan, Batangas.

Objectives

The feasibility study aimed to assess the viability and potential challenges of establishing a market in Barangay Tanagan, Calatagan, Batangas. To achieve this goal, the following key problem areas were addressed:

1. What is the level of demand for market in Barangay Tanagan Calatagan, Batangas?
2. What are the specific needs and preferences of the local community regarding market facilities and offerings?
3. What is the competitive landscape within Barangay Tanagan and the surrounding areas to attract customers and sustain profitability?
4. What are the logistical and infrastructure requirements for establishing a market in Barangay Tanagan, and how will the chosen location impact accessibility, convenience, and operational efficiency?
5. What are the legal and regulatory considerations that need to be addressed to establish and operate a market in Barangay Tanagan?
6. What are the potential risks and challenges associated with establishing and operating a market in Barangay Tanagan?
7. Based on the findings of the study, the researchers aim to propose a public market for Barangay Tanagan, Calatagan, Batangas.

Methodology

For assessing the needs of a market in Barangay Tanagan, Calatagan, Batangas, the researchers conducted a feasibility study to explore the factors influencing customer preferences for basic necessities in the marketplace. A feasibility study was crucial for understanding the practical aspects of research, allowing effective resource allocation, addressing ethical concerns, enhancing the validity and reliability of findings, and ensuring the applicability of research outcomes.

Population and Sampling

To collect information from the residents of Barangay Tanagan, the researchers used the 2020 Census, which had a total population of 4,224 residents. The researchers used Slovin's formula to calculate a sample size of 366 respondents, ensuring enough data for reliable insights.

Instrumentation

The research used structured survey questionnaires to gather data on customer preferences and satisfaction levels in a marketplace. The questionnaires covered demographics, demand, specific needs, competitive landscapes, logistics and infrastructure, legal and regulatory considerations, and potential risks. The study also included observation and secondary data analysis to complement the primary data. The results helped us understand the target market, competitor landscapes, logistics and infrastructure requirements, legal and regulatory frameworks, and potential risks to developing contingency plans. In addition, prior to the data gathering, the research instruments underwent rigorous validation, and revisions were incorporated.

Data Gathering and Procedures

The research started by clearly stating its goals and questions. Barangay Tanagan, with 4,224 individuals from Census 2020, was identified as the target population. Using Slovin's formula, a sample size of 366 respondents was determined for reliable insights. Random sampling ensured a diverse representation. Letters and informed consent were obtained, emphasizing voluntary participation and the right to withdraw. Carefully chosen data collection tools, like surveys or interviews, aligned with research goals. A plan for data analysis was developed post-collection to derive meaningful insights. Findings were presented in a comprehensive report, adhering to ethical standards and ensuring participant confidentiality. Results were shared, contributing to a broader understanding and informing future studies or interventions.

Data Analysis

The researchers used quantitative analysis methods, including frequency counts and weighted mean, to analyze customer preferences and evaluate market size. These statistical approaches helped identify patterns, trends, and correlations, providing insights into customer behavior.

Ethical Consideration

The study prioritized obtaining full consent from respondents, respecting their autonomy and privacy, and handling their data with strict confidentiality. Participants were informed about the research's purpose, procedures, and potential risks. Personal information was anonymized and stored separately from the data. The study adhered to ethical guidelines and regulations, safeguarding the well-being of participants. In cases involving vulnerable populations, informed consent was obtained from their legal guardians. Transparency was maintained throughout the research process, avoiding data manipulation and ensuring the conclusions were based on evidence.

Result and Discussion

This part thoroughly investigates the potential of establishing a market in the community by examining economic, social, and environmental factors through highlighting the benefits and challenges, offering a basis for informed decision-making and future planning.

Table 1

Level of demand for a market in Barangay Tanagan, Calatagan, Batangas

	Indicators	Mean	Interpretation	Rank
1.	The local community expresses a strong desire for a market in Barangay Tanagan.	4.240	Strongly Agree	2
2.	There is a noticeable demand for a variety of goods and services that a market could provide in Barangay Tanagan.	4.128	Agree	7
3.	Residents of Barangay Tanagan frequently travel to neighboring areas to fulfill their shopping needs.	4.199	Agree	4.5

4. The establishment of a market in Barangay Tanagan would significantly improve access to essential goods and services.	4.213	Strongly Agree	3
5. The local population has expressed support for the idea of having a market within Barangay Tanagan.	4.199	Agree	4.5
6. There is a demonstrated need for a market that caters to the preferences and demands of the residents in Barangay Tanagan.	4.175	Agree	6
7. The current lack of a market in Barangay Tanagan is viewed as a significant gap in the community's amenities.	4.295	Strongly Agree	1
GENERAL WEIGHTED MEAN	4.207	Agree	

The assessment of market demand in Barangay Tanagan, Calatagan, Batangas, reveals a strong local desire for a market. The community's expectations for a market should cater to diverse preferences, highlighting the importance of recognizing and responding to the diversity of consumer demands in local markets. The need for a market aligned with the preferences and demands of the residents is also evident, emphasizing the importance of understanding and responding to local preferences. Strong local support for a market is also evident, highlighting the importance of community buy-in for the success and sustainability of local development projects. The lack of a market is a significant gap in the community's amenities, highlighting the need for urgent attention. The community's willingness to travel for shopping needs is another indicator of the need for a market. This highlights the existing gap in local amenities and the potential economic outflow that a local market could address.

In conclusion, the absence of a market in Barangay Tanagan is a significant gap in community amenities, emphasizing the urgency of addressing this demand. By incorporating local perspectives in decision-making processes, the community can enhance access to essential goods and services, contribute to the overall well-being of the community, and contribute to the overall resilience and vibrancy of the community.

Table 2

The specific needs and preferences of the local community regarding market facilities and offerings

Indicators	Mean	Interpretation	Rank
1. The market should offer a wide variety of fresh produce.	4.290	Strongly Agree	15
2. A clean and well-maintained market environment is essential.	4.555	Strongly Agree	3
3. The market should have convenient parking facilities.	4.396	Strongly Agree	6
4. Availability of affordable products is important to me.	4.311	Strongly Agree	13
5. The market should have accessible restroom facilities.	4.243	Strongly Agree	18
6. I prefer markets that offer locally sourced products.	4.284	Strongly Agree	16
7. A covered area to protect shoppers from the weather is necessary.	4.219	Strongly Agree	19
8. The market should have options for organic or health-conscious products.	4.352	Strongly Agree	9
9. Prices at the market should be competitive with nearby alternatives.	4.172	Agree	20

10. Adequate seating or resting areas for shoppers should be available.	4.352	Strongly Agree	9
11. The market should provide opportunities for local artisans and vendors.	4.369	Strongly Agree	7
12. I value markets that promote eco-friendly practices (e.g., recycling bins).	4.478	Strongly Agree	4
13. Convenient payment options (e.g., digital payment methods) are important.	4.361	Strongly Agree	8
14. The market should have a diverse range of food vendors.	4.617	Strongly Agree	1
15. I prefer markets that offer cultural or specialty products unique to the area.	4.322	Strongly Agree	12
16. The market should have informational signage about products and vendors.	4.342	Strongly Agree	11
17. Friendly and knowledgeable market staff are essential.	4.404	Strongly Agree	5
18. I would be more likely to visit a market with entertainment or events.	4.260	Strongly Agree	17
19. I appreciate markets that support community initiatives or charities.	4.292	Strongly Agree	14
20. Adequate security measures are important for my peace of mind.	4.604	Strongly Agree	2
GENERAL WEIGHTED MEAN	4.361	Strongly Agree	

The market's pricing strategy should be competitive with nearby alternatives, reflecting the community's economic diversity and making it accessible to a wide range of residents. A covered area is essential for a comfortable shopping experience, especially during inclement weather. Accessible restroom facilities are also crucial, as they enhance convenience and satisfaction for shoppers.

The community's preference for markets offering locally sourced products is high, reflecting their affinity for supporting local economies and sustainable practices. This local-first approach contributes to community resilience and aligns with evolving consumer values. The market's strong preference for a rich variety of fresh produce is also evident, highlighting the community's commitment to supporting local agriculture and ensuring the availability of high-quality, fresh items for residents.

Markets that support community initiatives or charities are appreciated, as they contribute to the positive image and success of the market. Competitive pricing is essential for market success, as it impacts consumer satisfaction and loyalty. Cultural or specialty products unique to the area are also preferred, as they reflect and celebrate local culture.

Informational signage about products and vendors is essential, as it empowers consumers and facilitates informed choices in the market. This focus on information not only aligns with contemporary discussions on consumer empowerment but also positions the market as a transparent and communicative entity, fostering trust and understanding among its customers. Overall, the market's pricing strategies, amenities, and accessibility all contribute to its success and appeal to its community.

Table 3

Competitive landscape within Barangay Tanagan and the surrounding areas to attract customers and sustain profitability

Indicators	Mean	Interpretation	Rank
1. The local market in Barangay Tanagan has very few competitors offering similar products/services.	4.309	Strongly Agree	4
2. The surrounding areas have a lower concentration of businesses similar to the proposed market.	4.246	Strongly Agree	6
3. There is a low level of competition for customer attention and loyalty in Barangay Tanagan.	4.292	Strongly Agree	5
4. The existing competitors in the area have limited customer bases.	4.139	Agree	7
5. Competitors in the vicinity have a weak online presence that doesn't significantly impact customer choices.	4.413	Strongly Agree	2
6. The competitive pricing of existing businesses does not pose challenges to profitability.	3.596	Agree	8
7. Competing businesses have a poor reputation and lack customer trust.	2.923	Neutral	9
8. Existing competitors offer a narrow range of products/services that do not overlap with the proposed market's offerings.	4.331	Strongly Agree	3
9. Competing businesses lack effective marketing and promotional strategies.	4.587	Strongly Agree	1
GENERAL WEIGHTED MEAN	4.093	Agree	

The competitive landscape in Barangay Tanagan and its surrounding areas is characterized by several indicators. A neutral attitude towards competitors' reputations suggests businesses can capitalize on weaknesses to gain market share. Competitive pricing does not pose a risk to profitability, and competitors have limited customer bases. Businesses can build strong customer relationships and brand loyalty in less competition. Offering unique products or services can gain a competitive advantage. However, businesses lack effective marketing and promotion strategies.

Table 4

Logistical and infrastructure requirements for establishing a market in Barangay Tanagan, and how the chosen location will impact accessibility, convenience, and operational efficiency

Indicators	Mean	Interpretation	Rank
1. The availability of necessary infrastructure in Barangay Tanagan is sufficient for establishing a market.	4.440	Strongly Agree	7
2. The chosen location for the market is easily accessible by residents and potential customers.	4.615	Strongly Agree	2
3. The proposed market location ensures convenience for both vendors and customers.	4.372	Strongly Agree	8

4. The selected location enhances the operational efficiency of the market.	4.309	Strongly Agree	12
5. Adequate transportation facilities are in place to support market operations.	4.525	Strongly Agree	5
6. The existing utilities (e.g., electricity, water supply) meet the requirements of the market.	4.254	Strongly Agree	13
7. The proposed market location has sufficient parking facilities.	4.333	Strongly Agree	11
8. The chosen location minimizes potential bottlenecks or congestion.	4.541	Strongly Agree	4
9. The market proximity to major roads or transportation hub is advantageous for business	4.563	Strongly Agree	3
10. The infrastructure in the area can accommodate future expansion needs of the market.	4.443	Strongly Agree	6
11. The location ensures ease of delivery and transportation of goods to and from the market.	4.363	Strongly Agree	9
12. The infrastructure requirements align with the market's long-term sustainability goals.	4.650	Strongly Agree	1
13. The chosen location enhances the market's visibility to potential customers.	4.358	Strongly Agree	10
14. The infrastructure in Barangay Tanagan supports the market's technological needs (e.g., internet connectivity).	4.044	Agree	14
GENERAL WEIGHTED MEAN	4.415	Strongly Agree	

The study examines the infrastructure support for establishing a market in Barangay Tanagan, focusing on technological needs, utilities, operational efficiency, parking facilities, visibility, logistics, convenience, and community consensus. The research reveals that the chosen location not only suits but significantly enhances the market's operational efficiency, aligning with strategic implications. The proposed market location also boasts ample parking facilities, which significantly contribute to customer satisfaction and overall convenience.

The study also highlights the importance of visibility to potential customers, as well as the facilitation of ease in delivery and transportation of goods. The convenience experienced by vendors and customers at the proposed market location is also emphasized, as it contributes holistically to customer satisfaction and loyalty.

It emphasizes the importance of scalability and adaptability in market infrastructure for sustained long-term growth. The chosen location minimizes potential bottlenecks or congestion, enhancing the overall efficiency and attractiveness of market spaces. The strategic proximity to major roads or transportation hubs is a definitive business boon, as it validates the community's endorsement and provides nuanced insights into the operational advantages conferred by strategically chosen, congestion-free locations.

Conclude the infrastructure requirements align harmoniously with the market's long-term sustainability goals, providing a strategic perspective that resonates with the community's forward-thinking approach. Overall, the analysis of these indicators reveals a high level of agreement among community members regarding the logistical and infrastructure requirements for establishing a market in Barangay Tanagan.

Table 5

Legal and regulatory considerations that need to be addressed to establish and operate a market in Barangay Tanagan

Indicators	Mean	Interpretation	Rank
1. Business Registration	4.623	Strongly Agree	4
2. Business permits from the municipal government	4.792	Strongly Agree	1
3. Health permits	4.380	Strongly Agree	9
4. Environmental permits	4.270	Strongly Agree	16
5. Fire safety permits	4.281	Strongly Agree	15
6. Zoning and Land Use Regulations	4.301	Strongly Agree	13
7. Building and Construction Codes	4.265	Strongly Agree	17
8. Sanitation and Hygiene Standards	4.372	Strongly Agree	10
9. Food Safety Regulations	4.691	Strongly Agree	3
10. Vendor Licensing	4.459	Strongly Agree	8
11. Taxation and Financial Reporting	4.287	Strongly Agree	14
12. Labor Laws	4.317	Strongly Agree	12
13. Accessibility and Safety	4.500	Strongly Agree	6
14. Community Engagement	4.336	Strongly Agree	11
15. Environmental Impact Assessment	4.161	Agree	18
16. Vendor Regulations	4.500	Strongly Agree	6
17. Market Operating Hours	4.519	Strongly Agree	5
18. Waste Management	4.790	Strongly Agree	2
GENERAL WEIGHTED MEAN	4.436	Strongly Agree	

The community of Barangay Tanagan has a strong commitment to legal and regulatory considerations for the establishment and operation of a market. The community's agreement on environmental impact assessments, building and construction codes, environmental permits, fire safety permits, taxation and financial reporting, zoning and land use regulations, labor laws, community engagement, sanitation and hygiene standards, vendor licensing, market integrity, accessibility and safety, market operating hours, business registration, food safety regulations, waste management, and municipal business permits are all crucial for the community's success, safety, and sustainability.

The community's agreement on these indicators reflects its commitment to sustainable and responsible business practices, ensuring the safety of both vendors and customers. Compliance with building codes is essential for creating secure and resilient structures in public spaces, while environmental permits are not just a formality but also crucial for operating businesses within legal and ethical frameworks. Fire safety permits play a critical role in preventing and mitigating potential fire hazards, while taxation and financial reporting are essential for maintaining legal and financial credibility.

Community engagement fosters positive relationships, builds trust, and enhances overall market success. Sanitation and hygiene standards are crucial for preventing health risks and ensuring customer satisfaction. Vendor licensing contributes to fair business practices, consumer protection, and market integrity, while market operating hours ensure predictability and accessibility.

Business registration is crucial for legal recognition and transparency, while food safety regulations, public health and trust in marketplaces. Waste management is essential for environmental sustainability and community well-being, and municipal business permits ensure businesses align with local regulations. Overall, the community's agreement on these legal and regulatory considerations is a strong indication of their commitment to a successful and sustainable market.

Table 6

Potential risks and challenges associated with establishing and operating a market in Barangay Tanagan.

Indicators	Mean	Interpretation	Rank
1. Lack of Market Demand	4.667	Strongly Agree	2
2. Intense Competition from Existing Markets	4.828	Strongly Agree	1
3. High Initial Investment Costs	4.284	Strongly Agree	10
4. Operational Expenses Exceeding Projections	4.284	Strongly Agree	10
5. Difficulty in Sourcing Local Produce or Products	4.311	Strongly Agree	8
6. Transportation and Logistics Challenges	4.287	Strongly Agree	9
7. Regulatory and Permitting Hurdles	4.322	Strongly Agree	7
8. Environmental Impact Concerns	4.344	Strongly Agree	6
9. Community Resistance or Opposition	4.249	Strongly Agree	12
10. Access to Skilled Labor and Workforce Issues	4.366	Strongly Agree	5
11. Market Security and Safety Concerns	4.434	Strongly Agree	4
12. Sustainability and Resource Management Challenges	4.451	Strongly Agree	3
GENERAL WEIGHTED MEAN	4.402	Strongly Agree	

The community in Barangay Tanagan is aware of potential legal and regulatory challenges associated with establishing and operating a market. The community recognizes the importance of effective community engagement and transparent communication to address potential resistance. High initial investment costs are a significant financial challenge, and the community is aware of the need for meticulous financial planning and resource allocation. Operational expenses exceeding projections are another significant challenge, and the community is aware of the need for efficient transportation solutions. The community also recognizes the difficulty in sourcing local produce, which is crucial for market differentiation and community engagement. Regulatory and permitting hurdles are another significant concern, with the community recognizing the importance of legal compliance and regulatory navigation for the successful establishment and management of the market. Environmental impact concerns are also a significant concern, with the community recognizing the need to address these issues for the sustainable development of the market. Access to skilled labor and workforce issues is another significant challenge, with the community recognizing the importance of comprehensive workforce planning and development for market operations. Market security and safety concerns are also significant, with the community recognizing the need for a secure and safe market environment. The lack of market demand is a significant concern, and intense competition from existing markets is a significant factor. The community's collective awareness of these challenges and the need for strategic planning and mitigation strategies is crucial for the success and sustainability of the proposed market.

PUBLIC MARKET PROPOSAL TO BARANGAY TANAGAN, CALATAGAN, BATANGAS

Market Name: PAMILIHANG PANG MASA NG TANAGAN

It refers to a market or retail environment that focuses on serving the needs of the general public, particularly from the lower to middle-income segments. These markets often prioritize affordability and offer a wide range of goods and services at competitive prices. Aim to provide accessible options to a large number of people, addressing their day-to-day needs and preferences.

Market Logo:

This logo features a circular shape, symbolizing unity, and it also symbolizes supporting our local farmers and artisans with the local crops and products that they produce and make which the customers might give high satisfaction with regards to our concept and in connection with our core values.

Tagline: "Connecting Communities, Nurturing Sustainability"

Connecting Communities. This part of the tagline emphasizes the role of the market as a connecting force within a community. It suggests that the market serves as a gathering place where people from different backgrounds come together. It promotes a sense of unity, interaction, and social cohesion by providing a space for individuals to connect, communicate, and engage with one another.

Nurturing Sustainability. It suggests that the market is not only focused on economic transactions but also on promoting practices that are environmentally and socially responsible. It implies that the market aims to support sustainable agriculture, local producers, and environmentally friendly practices. By nurturing sustainability, the market demonstrates its concern for the well-being of the community and the environment.

The tagline reflects the market's dual focus on fostering community connections and nurturing sustainability. It conveys a message of a market that goes beyond being a mere commercial space, emphasizing its role as a catalyst for community interaction and a platform for sustainable practices. This tagline aims to appeal to individuals who value community engagement and sustainable living, positioning the market as a hub that aligns with their values.

Mission: To provide a dynamic and inclusive marketplace that customer can discover a diverse range of fresh produce, seafood, and an extensive selection of dry goods.

Vision: To be a top provider and source of budget-friendly daily necessities for perishable and non-perishable needs of customers in close vicinity within 2 years in Calatagan, Batangas

Goals:

1. To be the top provider of daily necessities within Calatagan, Batangas
2. To provide a good-quality product
3. Comparable quality that is always at the best price.
4. To be the first market in Tanagan

Market Description: Our market is dedicated to bringing you the highest-quality goods while supporting local farmers, artisans, and producers. From farm-fresh produce to handcrafted artisanal items, we have something for everyone who values wholesome, ethically sourced products. Supporting locally made products that can be offered to tourists is called “Pampasalubong goods,” which gives honor to Calatagan knowing that this town has such a great product that other people may love. This was an output from the creative minds of the students, in which it can be easily remembered by the customers and derived from the connectivity and eco-friendly unity of supporting to save our Mother Earth.

Fliers with Location

Front and Back Page

This flier shows the products and things that we offer in our market. Aside from the basic needs that we sell, we also have products that tourists may benefit from.

Location: Barangay Tanagan, Calatagan, Batangas, we chose this location because it has a huge space that is suitable for the market, is along the national road, and is surrounded by houses that can generate high sales in the market.

Conclusions

The market potential in Barangay Tanagan, Calatagan, Batangas is positive, with significant interest and support for establishing a local market. The local community's specific needs and preferences regarding market facilities and offerings are crucial for businesses to create a successful and sustainable business. Understanding the competitive landscape is essential for businesses to attract customers and sustain profitability. The chosen location of the market will impact accessibility, convenience, and operational efficiency. Key logistical requirements include sufficient storage space, efficient transportation networks, and reliable supply chains. Legal and regulatory considerations include business registration and licensing, health and safety regulations, and taxation and financial obligations. Tailoring strategies to the local context is crucial for a resilient and adaptable market operation. Regularly reviewing and updating this risk assessment will contribute to a more resilient and adaptable market operation.

Recommendations

The study underscores several key recommendations for the establishment and operation of a market in Barangay Tanagan. Firstly, it emphasizes the strategic importance of choosing a central and easily accessible location, fostering visibility and broadening the customer base. To effectively cater to the local community, the market is advised to tailor its facilities and offerings to meet specific needs and preferences, ensuring a more personalized and relevant customer experience. Developing a strong brand identity is highlighted as a crucial step to gain a competitive advantage in the market, fostering customer loyalty and distinguishing the market from competitors. It is imperative for the market to strictly adhere to local laws and regulations, fostering trust and credibility while preventing potential legal issues. Addressing potential risks and challenges proactively is recommended to enhance the market's resilience and operational effectiveness. Furthermore, targeted marketing campaigns focusing on local preferences are suggested to maximize the impact of promotional efforts and resonate effectively with the community. Consistently delivering superior products or services is considered paramount in building customer satisfaction and loyalty. Finally, the recommendation stresses the importance of proactive planning and adaptability in response to market dynamics, ensuring the market remains resilient and capable of adjusting to changing circumstances. By collectively implementing these recommendations, the study envisions a successful and sustainable market operation in Barangay Tanagan.

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